

HARMFUL IN FOODSTUFFS E APPENDIX

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6518935>

Mirsavirova D.M,
Riskidinova Z.X,
Ibragimov Sh.I,
M21 – 12 group master's students,
Jumaev B.M,
Akhrarov U.B,
Usmonjonova H.U.

Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology, Department of "Technology of canned meat and dairy products."

Food security means that people can eat at any time rich and safe (in terms of quality, quantity and diversity) of the elements they need for an active and healthy lifestyle. In the process of globalization, it has become important to provide the population of the country with quality and affordable food.

Food is one of the most important nutrients in human life. Consumers always want quality and safe products. By safe food we usually mean high quality, environmentally friendly products that do not contain harmful elements related to food, such as pesticides, harmful E additives. Food security is one of the major challenges facing humanity and determines the health, development and well-being of nations.

The quality of food consumed by the population is an important component of the level and quality of life of citizens and has a significant impact on the protection of the environment, as well as the socio-economic and demographic situation of the country. [1]

Food additives are substances that are invented in the laboratory or exist in nature. They are not used as independent food products. Only food additives are substances that are added for technological purposes to give them the desired properties during production, packaging, transportation or storage. Food additives affect the color, taste, smell, and texture of products.

According to the characteristics of the appendix E:

E 100 - 182 coloring additives;

E 200 - 299 bactericidal additives that prolong shelf life;

E 300 - 399 Additives that slow down the oxidation process and protect against oxidation (antioxidants and stabilizers);

E 400 - 499 stabilizer - additives that maintain the required strength (to form a uniform mass);

E 500 - 599 emulsifiers - additives responsible for homogeneity, additives that increase the acidity at the same time;

E 600 - 699 flavor enhancers;

E 700 - 899 backup indices;

E 900 - 999 anti-flammable additives, flour-enhancing, soothing, caring for the appearance of glazed products, preventing the formation of foam;

E 1100 - 1105 Enzymatic substances that preserve the appearance of the product. [2]

Harmful E supplements can be found in any food. Each food contains a limited amount of beneficial E supplements. Exceeding this amount can lead to various side effects. As an example, let's look at E-supplements in different foods based on Table 1:

Table 1

Product name	Additions of E
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● E 160b (annato) coloring ● E 320 (butylhydroxyanisole) ● E 321 (butylhydroxytoluene) ● E 202 (potassium sorbate) ● E 211 (sodium benzoate) ● E 471 (mono and diglyceride fatty acids) ● E 322 (soy lecithin) ● E 503 (ammonium carbonate) ● E 500 (sodium carbonate) ● E 450 (Pyrophosphate)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● E 903 (carnauba wax) ● E 100 (curcumin) ● E 162 (red beets) ● E 407 (fatty acids, salts of Al Ca Na Mg K and NH₄) ● E 414 (gum gum - Arabic gum) ● E 334 (vinoic acid) ● E 300 (vitamin C) ● E 330 (citric acid) ● E 296 (malic acid) ● E 160a (carotene) ● E 120 (carmine)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● E 1400 (dextrin) ● E 322 (soy lecithin) ● E 102 (tartrazine) ● E 104 (yellow quinoline) ● E 110 (yellow, sunset) ● E 122 (azorubin, karmoisin) ● E 124 (Ponso 4R, cochineal red <p>A)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● E 129 (charming red AC) ● E 133 (bright blue FCF) ● E 171 (titanium dioxide) ● E 903 (carnauba wax)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● E 330 (citric acid) ● E 414 (gum gum - Arabic gum) ● E 415 (xanthan gum) ● E 202 (potassium sorbate) ● E 300 (vitamin C) ● E 160d (lycopene) ● E 960 (stevioside)

Food supplements E are divided into 3 groups:

- Of course
- A mixture of natural and artificial
- Completely synthetic

According to Table 1, we see the results of the analysis of supplements E in food:

1. Harmful E additives and side effects for the human body in the confectionery product "Yashkino (myagkie waffles with cherry jam)":

- E 320 is butylhydroxyanisole (synthetic), an antioxidant that slows down the oxidation process and protects against oxidation. Supplement E 320 is widely used as a preservative additive, especially in fatty foods, confectionery and meat products. An overdose of butylhydroxyanisole interacts with nitrates in the human body, causing mutations in DNA cells, causing allergies, liver and stomach damage. It is safe to consume 0.5 mg / kg body weight per day. [3]

- E 321 - butylhydroxytoluene (synthetic, similar to E320). Overdose of butylhydroxytoluene causes hyperactivity in some children and increases the risk of cancer.

•E 211 - sodium benzoate (a mixture of natural and artificial), is an additive that prolongs the shelf life, protects against bacteria. Supplement E 211 is widely used in the production of meat and fish, sweetened carbonated beverages, confectionery, salmon, ketchup, mayonnaise. An excess of sodium benzoate leads to a decrease in hemoglobin levels, the development of leukemia, cirrhosis of the liver, Parkinson's disease. [4]

2. Tic tac (mint, fruit mixture and berry mixture dragees) contains harmful E supplements and side effects for the human body:

•E 100 - turmeric. It is a food coloring additive. Supplement E 100 is widely used in the manufacture of confectionery, beverages, sausages, dragees, marmalades. Excess curcumin can cause miscarriage during pregnancy, react with elements in the body and have toxic effects. [5]

3. Harmful E supplements and side effects for M & M's (milk chocolate and peanut chocolate candies):

•E 133 - bright blue FCF, (synthetic). It is a food coloring additive. Supplement E 100 is widely used in the manufacture of confectionery, beverages, sausages, dragees, marmalades. Supplement E 133 - Poorly absorbed in the intestinal tract, leading to suffocation attacks in asthmatics and allergic reactions, especially in people sensitive to aspirin.

•E 122 - azorubin, carmoisin, (synthetic). It is a food coloring additive. Supplement E 100 is widely used in the manufacture of confectionery, beverages, sausages, dragees, marmalades and juices. Supplement E 122 has a number of side effects. Allergic reactions in the form of rash on the skin, increased bronchial asthma, increased hyperactivity in children and a decrease in concentration are observed. [6]

•E 110 - yellow, sunset, (synthetic). It is a food coloring additive. Supplement E 100 is widely used in the manufacture of confectionery, orange and peach jelly, dragees, marmalade juices. It is a carcinogen, causes allergic reactions, side effects such as nausea, rhinitis, rash, swelling of the kidneys, chromosomal damage, indigestion, vomiting, abdominal pain and loss of appetite.

•E 124 - Ponso 4R, cochineal red A (synthetic).). It is a food coloring additive. Supplement E 124 is widely used in the manufacture of confectionery, ice cream, soft drinks, canned fruit, desserts. It is a carcinogen that triggers the development of cancer, is a potential allergen that can cause anaphylactic shock or asthma attacks in people with asthma and aspirin allergies, and causes hyperactivity in children.

•E 104 - yellow quinoline, (synthetic). It is a food coloring additive. Supplement E 104 is widely used in the manufacture of alcoholic and non-alcoholic beverages, confectionery, candies, jelly quality confectionery. It causes various skin inflammations, allergic reactions, asthma attacks, anaphylactic shock and death in 10-20%.

•E 102 - tartrazine (synthetic). It is a food coloring additive. Supplement E 102 is widely used in the manufacture of ice cream, canned fruit, cakes, desserts, yogurt, hot and

carbonated beverages. E 102 has high levels of allergies, leading to impaired brain function, decreased attention span, and cracked tongue and facial nerve palsy. [7]

4. "Love is... (strawberry - banana and cherry - lemon non-alcoholic, carbonated drink)" contains harmful E supplements and side effects for the human body:

- E 202 is a potassium sorbate, a shelf-life supplement, and a bactericidal supplement. It is widely used in canning juice, margarine, sauces, mayonnaise, confectionery, chocolate, wine and soft drinks. Causes irritation of mucous membranes and skin.

- E 960 is a stevioside, an anti-flammable supplement that improves the appearance of flour, softens, cares for the appearance of glazed products, prevents the formation of foam. Side effects include dizziness, nausea, and gastrointestinal upset. [8]

In conclusion, harmful E additives in food lead to the development of various diseases in the human body. We even found that some E supplements can be lethal in excess of 10-20%. Particular attention should be paid to the composition of any exported and imported food products, to prevent the consumption of food products that are harmful to the human body. The most important thing is to strictly control the composition of the food produced, the additives E to be added, and to add natural additives instead of the additives E. For example, most of the coloring additives E are synthetic additives and have been shown to have a number of side effects for the human body. Adding naturally occurring coloring additives instead of synthetic coloring supplements will be beneficial to the health of the population and a significant increase will be made. In short, the safety of food is important for human health.

BIBLIOGRAPHY:

1. A.Umarov. The urgency of food safety and the importance of restricting the production of genetically modified organisms (GMOs). Academic research in education sciences Vol. 2, Issue 1, 2021, 868-878 b.
2. <https://dobavkam.net/>
3. Yashin A.Ya., Yashin Ya.I., Chernousov N.I. Opredelenie prirodnyx antioxidantov // Pishchevaya promishlennost. 2006. № 2. S. 10 - 12.
4. Sarafanova L.A. Pishchevye additions: Encyclical. - SPb.: Giord, 2003 - 688 p.
5. Bolotov V.M., Nechaev A.P., Sarafanova L.A. Pishchevye krasiteli: klassifikatsiya, svoystva, analiz i primenenie. SPb.: Giord, 2008 - 83 p
6. Pishchevye krasiteli: E.V.Smirnov - Moscow, Professiya, 2009. - 354 s.
7. <http://Calorizator.ru>
8. Kharitonov S.N., Razreshennye i zapreshchennyye pishchevyye dobavki. - Journal * Spros *, №7.